

Effect of surface charge of phospholipid membranes on the photophysics of a 4'-(diethylamino)-3-hydroxyflavone dye

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Manuscript received online 07 December 2012, revised 09 January 2013, accepted 11 March 2013

Abstract : The photophysics of a dye, *N*-[[4'-*N,N*-diethylamino-3-hydroxy-6-flavonyl]methyl]-*N*-methyl-*N*-(3-sulfopropyl)-1-dodecanaminium, inner salt (F2N12S), in the large unilamellar vesicles of neutral egg yolk phosphatidylcholine (EYPC) and negatively charged egg yolk phosphatidylglycerol (EYPG) lipids were investigated by steady state and time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy. The fluorescence spectra display a dramatic variation of the relative intensity of dual emission bands attributed to the normal (N*) and tautomer (T*) excited states of the dye, which is attributed to the faster excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) kinetics in the neutral vesicles with a time constant (τ_{PT}) of ~ 16 ps compared to the slower ESIPT ($\tau_{PT} \sim 33$ ps) in the anionic lipid vesicles. Furthermore, a significantly slower solvent relaxation dynamics with an average relaxation time (τ_S) of ~ 1.38 ns is manifested in the neutral EYPC vesicles relative to a faster solvent relaxation ($\tau_S \sim 0.91$ ns) in the negatively charged EYPG vesicles.

Keywords : ESIPT, solvent relaxation, TRES.

Introduction

Several key biological processes such as the rate of membrane fusion, the partitioning of proteins and peptides into biological membranes, the transport of solutes through membrane are regulated by the membrane surface charge¹. The electrostatic character of the individual lipid head groups, lipid intermolecular association and their transbilayer distribution across the membranes significantly modulate the physical properties of these membranes²⁻⁴. Hydration of the lipid bilayer surface and charge repulsion at the lipid head group level influence the intrinsic membrane curvature and associated strain⁵, which is likely responsible for the cellular regulation of a number of biological activities^{6,7}. The water molecules can penetrate deeply into the bilayer and have hydration effects at the level of phosphate and carbonyl groups, as evident from IR and Raman spectroscopic studies^{8,9}. Hydration is likely to be stronger when the electrostatic repulsion between the negatively charged phosphate groups are not counter-balanced by positive charges of the lipid heads. For instance, IR and Raman spectroscopy^{8,9} have

revealed stronger hydration of two phospholipid ester carbonyl groups in phosphatidylglycerol (PG) containing negative charge on the phosphate group, compared to the zwitterionic phosphatidylcholine (PC). The water molecules provide a dielectric stabilization of the dipoles of lipid heads, thereby, producing a dramatic modulation of the interfacial dipolar potential¹⁰⁻¹². The coupling of lipid hydration and interfacial dipolar potential is poorly understood, due to a limited amount of evidence¹³⁻¹⁵ which stems from the limitations of the experimental methods and the lack of fluorescent dyes suitable for studying the effects of lipid charge on the bilayer hydration. The charged fluorescence probes like ANS^{16,17} can not protrude deeply into the bilayer, while the neutral ones e.g. Laurdan or Prodan are not sensitive enough to the effects of charge¹⁸⁻²⁰. Moreover, the commonly used polarity-sensitive and electrochromic dyes are effective only to a limited extent as they provide the response by shifting the broad band already present in the emission spectrum^{21,22}.

In this regard, two-color ratiometric probes e.g. F and F2N8 (Fig. 2a) based on 3-hydroxyflavone showed a

great promise in probing the electrostatic potential at the surface layer of the phospholipid membranes^{23,24}, which is based on potential-dependent changes of the bilayer hydration. Their two band (color) ratiometric response in the steady state emission spectra arises from an excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) reaction (Fig. 2b), which gives rise to dual fluorescence with two well resolved emission bands attributed to the initially excited normal (N*) and proton-transferred tautomer (T*) forms, respectively. The ratio (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) of intensities of these two emission bands for the two probes F and F2N8 was found to be a sensitive parameter of perturbations in the lipid-water interfaces^{23,24} resulting from a variation of surface charge on the phospholipid membranes. As the (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) ratio is modulated by the dynamics of an ESIPT reaction and factors influencing it²⁵, the study of the proton transfer dynamics by means of time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy is likely to enlighten us with the underlying causes behind the differential ratiometric response for such probes in phospholipid vesicles bearing different surface charges. Earlier²⁶, we observed the simultaneous occurrence of both ESIPT and solvent relaxation phenomena in the photophysics of F2N12S (Fig. 1), an improved analogue of F2N8, in the large unilamellar vesicles of EYPC and DOPC with a zero surface charge, which comprised zwitterionic PC lipids. In the present report, which employed a time-resolved fluorescence set up with a much better time resolution of ~ 10 ps than that used earlier²⁶, we provide with the results of comparative studies on F2N12S in neutral and anionic vesicles composed of zwitterionic EYPC and negatively charged EYPG phospholipids (Fig. 1), respectively.

Materials and methods :

The phospholipids egg yolk phosphatidylcholine (EYPC) and phosphatidylglycerol (EYPG) were from Sigma. The probe F2N12S was synthesized as described earlier²⁷. Large unilamellar vesicles (LUV) of 200 μ M lipid concentration were obtained in 15 mM phosphate-citrate buffer, pH 7.0, by the classical extrusion method²⁸. LUVs were labeled by adding an aliquot of the dye stock solution in DMSO to a final concentration of 2 μ M. In LUVs labeled with the probe, DMSO was always $\leq 0.1\%$ v/v.

Absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded at

20 °C on Cary 4 spectrophotometer (Varian) and FluoroMax 3.0 (Jobin Yvon, Horiba) spectrofluorometer, respectively. Time-resolved fluorescence measurements were performed with the time-correlated, single-photon counting technique using the frequency-doubled output of a Ti-sapphire laser at 426 nm (Tsunami, Spectra Physics) pumped by a Millennia X laser as discussed in details elsewhere²⁶. The full width at half-maximum of the instrument response function was ~ 40 ps. The time-resolved decays were analyzed together with instrument response functions using an iterative reconvolution method²⁹ which provided an effective time resolution of ~ 10 ps. The goodness of the fit was evaluated from the χ^2 values, the plots of the residuals and the autocorrelation function.

Time-resolved emission spectra (TRES) were generated from a set of emission decays (at least 18 wavelengths) recorded at 10 nm intervals spanning the fluorescence spectrum using the "Spectral Reconstruction" method as described elsewhere³⁰⁻³². The time evolution of the peak frequencies $\nu(t)$ in the TRES were fitted using a sum of two log-normal line shape functions :

$$F(\nu, t) = \sum_{i=1}^2 g_i \exp \{ -\ln 2 (\ln [1 + 2b_i(\nu - \nu_i)/\Delta_i]/b_i)^2 \} \quad \alpha > 1 \quad (1)$$

$$= 0, \text{ for } \alpha \leq 1 \text{ where } \alpha = 2b_i(\nu - \nu_i)/\Delta_i$$

where g_i , ν_i , b_i and Δ_i are the peak height, peak frequency, asymmetry parameter and width parameter respectively. The solvation response or correlation function $C(t)$ was calculated according to :

$$C(t) = \frac{\nu(t) - \nu(\infty)}{\nu(0) - \nu(\infty)} \quad (2)$$

where $\nu(0)$ and $\nu(\infty)$ correspond to the peak frequency values obtained by "time-zero estimation" and infinity time, respectively.

The peak frequency at $t = 0$, which is not directly measurable, was calculated using the approximation proposed by Fee *et al.*³³ :

$$\nu(0) \approx \nu_{np}(\text{em}) - \nu_{np}(\text{abs}) + \nu_p(\text{abs}) \quad (3)$$

where the indices "np" and "p" refer to the steady-state

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Fig. 1. Structural representation of phospholipids.

Fig. 2. (a) Structure and probable location of the probes F, F2N8, F2N12S in phospholipid membranes and (b) excited state intramolecular proton transfer of 4'-(dialkylamino)-3-hydroxyflavone, N^* and T^* are the excited normal and proton-transferred tautomers, respectively.

peak frequencies measured in nonpolar and polar solvents, respectively, and the terms “em” and “abs” in the parentheses denote the steady state fluorescence and absorption peak frequencies respectively.

The decomposition of the steady state fluorescence

spectra into three log-normal components were performed as described elsewhere³⁴. For this purpose, the spectrum of an individual component on the frequency scale was assumed to be reasonably well described by a quadriparametric log-normal function³⁵.

Results and discussion

Steady-state spectroscopy :

The steady state emission spectra of F2N12S display dual emission in the large unilamellar vesicles (LUVs) of EYPC and EYPG (Fig. 3) with maxima at ~ 515 – 522 nm and ~ 563 – 572 nm, respectively, similar to its closely related analogues F2N8²⁴ and 4'-(dimethylamino)-hydroxyflavone (F)³⁶. Several features of the steady state emission spectra, namely, the shape and position of the short-wavelength emission band, and ratio of intensity of these dual emission bands are noteworthy when compared between neutral and anionic LUVs.

Fig. 3. Fluorescence spectra of F2N12S in LUVs at 293 K. λ_{exc} was 420 nm.

The broad spectral profile of the short-wavelength emission band (Fig. 3) of F2N12S in EYPC and EYPG vesicles at ~ 520 nm is similar to DOPC²⁷ and analogous fluorescent dyes F2N8 and F in lipid bilayers^{24,36} and may be attributed to the superposition of the N* and H-N* bands (Fig. 4) corresponding to an emission of the intramolecularly H-bonded and intermolecularly H-bonded forms, respectively^{26,36}. In the ground state, there exists an intramolecular hydrogen bond between the 4-carbonyl and the 3-hydroxy moieties of F2N12S in the intramolecularly H-bonded form (N), whereas in the intermolecularly H-bonded form (H-N) an intermolecular hydrogen bond between the 4-carbonyl oxygen and water molecule prevails without any intramolecular H-bond. On the other hand, the longer-wavelength emission band at

~ 570 nm may be attributed to the proton-transferred T* form (Fig. 2b). The decomposition of the fluorescence spectra into individual log-normal components (Fig. 4) showed further the location of the N*, H-N* and T* bands at ~ 500 nm, 540 nm and 580 nm, respectively (Table 1). Furthermore, the excitation spectra of F2N12S at the blue edge (~ 480 nm) and peak maximum (~ 580 nm) of the N* and T* bands, respectively, are identical and closely resemble the corresponding absorption spectrum in addition to being blue shifted by ~ 3 nm (Fig. 5) from the excitation spectrum monitored at the H-N* band (~ 540 nm). These observations confirm (i) the origin of the N* and T* bands from the intramolecularly H-bonded form (N) in the ground state and (ii) the presence of two ground state species in the lipid bilayers of EYPC and EYPG, namely, the intramolecularly H-bonded (N) form and the intermolecularly H-bonded form (H-N)²⁶.

Fig. 3 demonstrates a distinct difference between the fluorescence spectrum, when the dye F2N12S is incorporated into the large unilamellar vesicles of different surface charges. The decrease of negative charge per lipid molecule from -1 (for EYPG) to 0 (for EYPC) significantly decreases the contribution of the N* band relative to the T* band, and as a consequence, the $I_{\text{N}^*}/I_{\text{T}^*}$ ratio decreases from 2.64 to 1.47 (Table 1). The polarity of the dye environment in the binding sites of these phospholipid vesicles of different surface charges is more or less similar as evident from the absence of any observable shift in position of the N* band, since it is known to be sensitive to solvent polarity on account of the significantly large dipole moment of the N* form compared to its dipole moment in the ground state²⁶. The results of decomposition of the fluorescence spectra into individual components (Fig. 4) exhibit that the emission maximum corresponding to the N* form in EYPC (498 nm) is similar to that in EYPG (499 nm) vesicles (Table 1). The increase of the $I_{\text{N}^*}/I_{\text{T}^*}$ ratio may be attributed to an increase of polarity and hydrogen-bonding ability of the local environment of the dye, which is likely to provide a dielectric stabilization of the N* form owing to its higher dipole moment^{23,24}.

However, the absence of any difference of the emission maximum of the N* form between the EYPC and EYPG vesicles, indicates to the more important role of the hydrogen-bonding ability than the polarity of the dye

Fig. 4. Decomposition of the fluorescence spectra into log-normal components.

Table 1. Steady state photophysical parameters of F2N12S at 293 K

LUV	λ_{N^*} (nm)	λ_{T^*} (nm)	λ_{H-N^*} (nm)	I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}	$\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$ (cm^{-1})
EYPC	498	579	541	1.47	2809
EYPG	499	578	543	2.64	2739

λ_{N^*} , λ_{H-N^*} and λ_{T^*} are emission maxima of the excited normal, intermolecularly hydrogen-bonded, and the proton-transferred tautomer forms, respectively, obtained from the log-normal decomposition of the fluorescence spectra^{34,35}. I_{N^*}/I_{T^*} is the ratio of intensities of the N^* and T^* bands, $\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$ is the difference of emission maxima of the N^* and T^* bands, on frequency scale.

environment in modulation of the intensity ratio (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}). This is further evident from the lower value of the ($\nu_{N^*} -$

ν_{T^*}) parameter in EYPG vesicles than the EYPC vesicles (Table 1), which reflects a stronger hydrogen bonding environment of F2N12S in the former than the latter since lower ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) was ascribed to result from intermolecular H-bonding interactions^{25,37}. The oxygen atom of the 4-carbonyl group in F2N12S, being the site of intermolecular H-bonding interaction, possesses an effective negative charge in the N^* state, while in the T^* state this negative charge is compensated by the transferred proton, leading to a selective stabilization of the N^* state and destabilization of the T^* state by water molecules in the lipid vesicles which likely contributes to the lower ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) in EYPG vesicles than EYPC. So, the observed dra-

matic variation of the ratio of the band intensities, may be ascribed to differential hydration^{23,24} of the binding sites in the lipid bilayers of EYPC and EYPG. To further probe the role of differential hydration of the lipid bilayers in the significant difference of the steady state fluorescence spectrum, time-resolved fluorescence measurements were carried out.

Time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy :

The time-resolved fluorescence decays (Fig. 6) of F2N12S in lipid vesicles are strongly wavelength-depen-

dent, and are fastest when monitored at the blue edge of the steady state emission spectra at ~ 460 nm, and slowest at the red edge (~ 600 nm and above) of the T* band. The decays monitored at all of the emission wavelengths spanning the steady-state spectrum (~ 460 – 630 nm) are multiexponential with 3–4 components. A fast decay component (τ_1) of ~ 16 – 33 ps with a significant amplitude is observed at the blue edge (~ 460 nm) of the N* band, whereas an identical rise component of ~ 18 – 34 ps is systematically observed with a negative amplitude

Fig. 5. Excitation spectra of F2N12S in EYPC vesicles.

Fig. 6. Time-resolved fluorescence decays of F2N12S in lipid vesicles. Dashed (---) and solid (—) curves represent raw and fitted decay traces. Excitation wavelength is 427 nm.

(Table 2) at the red edge (~ 610 nm) of the tautomer (T^*) band. Thus, the rise of the tautomer emission, within experimental error, correlates well with the decay dynamics of the normal (N^*) species, which indicates to a precursor-successor type of relationship between the N^* and T^* forms, thereby, confirming the occurrence of an ESIPT reaction, $N^* \rightarrow T^*$ (Fig. 2b). It is quite pertinent to

mention that the fast decay or rise component of ~ 16 – 18 ps observed for EYPC vesicles is significantly different from what was observed earlier²⁶. This is most possibly due to the lower time resolution (~ 15 – 20 ps) of the earlier²⁶ TCSPC set up compared to the better time resolution (~ 10 ps) of the TCSPC set up used in the present study.

Table 2. Time-resolved fluorescence data of F2N12S (2 μ M) in LUVs (200 μ M, pH 7.0) at 20 °C

LUV	λ (nm)	τ_1	α_1	τ_2	α_2	τ_3	α_3	τ_4	α_4	χ^2
EYPC	460	0.016	0.62	0.123	0.24	0.460	0.10	2.29	0.04	1.05
	490	0.071	0.30	0.270	0.29	0.734	0.22	2.66	0.19	1.05
	510			0.112	0.29	0.673	0.35	2.79	0.36	1.00
	540			0.280	-0.10	0.718	0.27	2.96	0.73	1.16
	610	0.018	-0.81	0.266	-0.19	0.783	0.14	2.88	0.86	1.08
EYPG	460	0.033	0.47	0.147	0.28	0.508	0.17	2.20	0.08	0.97
	490	0.082	0.27	0.274	0.20	0.780	0.28	2.63	0.25	0.93
	510			0.175	0.20	0.911	0.35	2.88	0.45	1.09
	540			0.110	-0.17	0.826	0.10	2.92	0.90	1.01
	610	0.034	-0.80	0.240	-0.20			2.78	1.00	1.14

τ_1 , τ_2 , τ_3 and τ_4 – decay times (ns), α_1 , α_2 , α_3 and α_4 – pre-exponential coefficients, χ^2 – goodness of the fit, obtained after deconvolution of the corresponding decay curves. The estimated error of the decay times is $< \pm 10\%$, λ is the emission wavelength for recording fluorescence decays.

The time-resolved emission decays at both ~ 460 and 610 nm also display an identical long-lived decay component (τ_4) of ~ 2.3 – 2.9 ns which likely corresponds to the decay time (radiative plus non-radiative decay) of the N* and T* forms. This longest decay component (τ_4) remains more or less fixed, but its amplitude increases upon going from the blue edge to the red edge of the monitored wavelength range.

The two pre-exponential coefficients (α_1 and α_4), describing the rise and decay of the T* form at 610 nm are more or less similar in magnitude but opposite in sign (Table 2), which is consistent with the model of a reversible ESIPT reaction²⁶. This is quite reasonable because the decay time of the ESIPT tautomer is roughly 100-fold larger than the fastest component attributed to ESIPT. In consequence, a fast equilibrium is established between the normal (N*) and the tautomer (T*) excited states, in which the rates of both forward and reverse ESIPT are much faster than the decay (radiative plus non-radiative) rate for both states. The fast decay component (τ_1) remains more or less constant at ~ 16 – 33 ps in the blue edge (~ 460 – 480 nm) of the N* band, but increases in magnitude and decreases in amplitude on moving further towards the red with its complete disappearance in the range of ~ 510 – 550 nm. The increase of magnitude of the fast component (τ_1) at an wavelength of 490 nm and above and its complete disappearance (Table 2) in the range of 510 – 550 nm suggests the occurrence of an additional decay channel, other than ESIPT for the deactiva-

tion of the N* form. The time-resolved emission decays are also characterized by another two decay components, τ_2 (~ 120 – 260 ps) and τ_3 (~ 0.5 – 0.8 ns) at all of the monitored wavelengths, but their amplitudes are wavelength-dependent. The shorter component, τ_2 , which decays with a positive amplitude in the monitored wavelength range of 460 – 510 nm, evolves as a rise component at an wavelength of 540 nm and above (Table 2). The evolution of τ_2 as a rise component at 540 nm, where the emission is predominantly from the H-N* form (Fig. 4), indicates to an excited state transformation of the N* form into the H-N* form. Following the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition, the N* species possesses a large dipole moment due to an intramolecular charge transfer (Fig. 2b), which induces dipolar relaxation and a localized hydrogen-bonding interaction of a water molecule with the 4-carbonyl group of F2N12S leading to the formation of the H-N* species in the lipid bilayer²⁶. This is quite likely, as the intramolecular charge transfer renders the 4-carbonyl group of a 4'-(dialkylamino)-3-hydroxyflavone dye, a strong H-bond acceptor in the excited state^{37,38}.

The amplitude of the longer component (τ_3) is positive at all of the monitored wavelengths and is most pronounced (10–35%) in the range of 510 – 540 nm (Table 2), suggesting that this component likely describes the decay of the solvent relaxed H-N* species²⁶.

Time-resolved emission spectra (TRES) :

The temporal evolution of the emission spectra

Fig. 7. Time-resolved emission spectra (TRES) of F2N12S in LUVs at different delay times.

(Fig. 7) displays signatures, characteristic of both ESIPT and solvent relaxation in the photophysics of the F2N12S dye in the large unilamellar vesicles of EYPC and EYPG. ESIPT is manifested in the fast growth of the longer-wavelength emission band at $\sim 570\text{--}580\text{ nm}$ on a time scale of few hundreds of pico-seconds, whereas solvent relaxation is demonstrated by the time dependent Stokes shift of the short-wavelength band to the red on a nano-

second time scale. The time-dependent Stokes shift of the N^* band to the red associated with solvent relaxation, along with the growth of the T^* band, which is ascribed to an ESIPT reaction, become clearly evident in the normalized spectral evolution of the TRES (Fig. 8). Moreover, the time-resolved area normalized emission spectra³⁹ (TRANES) of F2N12S in EYPC and EYPG also exhibit a continuous red shift of spectral peak of the N^*

Fig. 8. Normalized spectral evolution of TRES in LUVs at different delay times.

band along with the growth of the T^* band. Absence of an isoemissive point in TRANES (Figure not shown) shows that the time dependent Stokes shift in LUVs originates from multiple emissive species, for which, the salvation model based on a continuous distribution of energy levels between the initially excited N^* form and a final relaxed N^* form, is more appropriate. All of these spectral features of the time-resolved spectra can be rationalized by the model of Das *et al.*²⁶, where (Scheme 1) it is hypothesized that apart from the population decay (radiative and

non-radiative) two other decay channels, namely, a fast and reversible ESIPT ($N^* \leftrightarrow T^*$) and solvent relaxation ($N^* \rightarrow H-N^*$), compete for the deactivation of the hydrogen-bond free N^* form in the S_1 state. The ground state heterogeneity, namely the presence of N (intramolecularly H-bonded) and $H-N$ (intermolecularly H-bonded) forms^{36,40} in the ground state is also taken into account in this model²⁶ where photo-excitation of $H-N$ form provides an alternative radiative channel to the formation of $H-N^*$ species.

Scheme 1. Photophysical processes of F2N12S in lipid bilayers. H-N* - Intermolecularly hydrogen-bonded normal form, N* - Intramolecularly hydrogen bonded normal form, T* - ES IPT tautomer form. “Reprinted with permission from Ref. 26 Copyright {2012} American Chemical Society”.

Kinetics of ES IPT and solvent relaxation in lipid bilayers :

At an early time (0.02–0.04 ns, Fig. 8) following photoexcitation, the short-wavelength band is displayed at ~480–490 nm with the simultaneous appearance of a significantly weak T* band at ~570–580 nm. This demonstrates the formation of the proton-transferred tautomer (T*) from the N* form through ES IPT in a time of less than 40 ps because the short-wavelength band at ~490 nm is attributed to the intramolecularly H-bonded normal (N) form (Table 1, Fig. 1). TRES (Figs. 7 and 8) also reveal that, at later times (0.08–0.16 ns) the T* band grows in intensity at the expense of the N* band confirming further the formation of the T* form via an ES IPT transformation of the N* form. In addition, on a longer timescale (0.04–2.0 ns), the transformation of the N* species into H-N* species through solvent relaxation is observed resulting in a continuous time-dependent Stokes shift of the N* band to the red. The N*→H-N* transformation through solvent relaxation involves dielectric relaxation and localized hydrogen-bonding interaction of a water molecule with the 4-carbonyl group of the F2N12S dye²⁶. Moreover, the manifestation of this dynamic Stokes shift over a much longer time window (0.04–2.0 ns) compared to the time scale (0.04–0.25 ns) for growth of the T* band, indicates to a distinctly slower kinetics of solvent relaxation than ES IPT.

ES IPT kinetics :

The identical decay or rise component (~16–34 ps) corresponding to the time-resolved fluorescence decays at the blue edge (~460 nm) of the N* band or the red edge (~610 nm) of the T* band (Table 2), may be assigned to the time constant (τ_{PT}) of the proton-transfer reaction for providing us with a qualitative estimate of the ES IPT dynamics, because both solvent relaxation and population decay (radiative plus non-radiative process) compete with ES IPT for the deactivation of the N* form (Scheme 1). The ES IPT time constants (~16–34 ps) for F2N12S in the large unilamellar vesicles of EYPC and EYPG are in mutual agreement with the ES IPT time constant of a few tens of picoseconds for 4'-N,N-(dimethylamino)-3-hydroxyflavone in the polar, aprotic solvents of acetonitrile, N,N-dimethylformamide or dichloromethane^{41–43}.

Moreover, the time constant of the ES IPT (Table 2) reaction of F2N12S are significantly different between EYPC (τ_{PT} ~16 ps) and EYPG vesicles (τ_{PT} ~33 ps), and indicates to a slower ES IPT dynamics in EYPG than EYPC which correlates well with the ratio of intensities (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) of the N* and T* bands (Table 1), since lower value of (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) implies a faster proton-transfer dynamics and vice-versa²⁵. The slower ES IPT rate in EYPG than EYPC is not likely to originate from an appreciably large solvent polarity induced barrier⁴³ in the former because of the similar polarity of the dye environment in both of these vesicles as discussed earlier. So, the observed difference of the ES IPT dynamics between EYPG and EYPC likely originates from the differential hydration of the dye environment in these vesicles, for which, the slower proton-transfer dynamics in the EYPG vesicles than EYPC may be attributed to a greater weakening of the intramolecular H-bond between the 3-hydroxy and the 4-carbonyl moieties of the N* form (Fig. 2a), by an intermolecular H-bonding interaction between the 4-carbonyl oxygen and water molecules⁴⁴. Therefore, we conjecture that stronger hydration of the binding sites of F2N12S in the lipid vesicles of EYPG than EYPC, induces a stronger intermolecular H-bonding perturbation of the intramolecular hydrogen bond between the 3-hydroxy and the 4-carbonyl moieties of F2N12S (Fig. 2a), thereby, leading to a slower ES IPT dynamics and vice-versa. Indeed, greater hydration of the phospholipid ester

Fig. 9. Time-dependent decay of the solvent correlation function, $C(t)$ in lipid vesicles.

Table 3. Decay components in the solvent relaxation of F2N12S in LUV

LUV	ϕ_1 (ns)	a_1	ϕ_2 (ns)	a_2	ϕ_3 (ns)	a_3	$\langle \tau_s \rangle$ (ns)
EYPC	0.058	0.29	0.435	0.44	4.34	0.27	1.38
EYPG	0.112	0.35	1.34	0.65			0.91

$\langle \tau_s \rangle = \int_0^{\infty} C(t) dt$ = average solvent relaxation time. ϕ_1, ϕ_2, ϕ_3 are the solvent relaxation components, a_1, a_2 and a_3 are the corresponding pre-exponential coefficients.

carbonyl groups (sn_1 and sn_2) in negatively charged phosphatidylglycerol (PG) compared to zwitterionic phosphatidylcholine (PC) vesicles were demonstrated by IR and Raman spectroscopy^{8,9}. Moreover, the probe F2N12S, which is a structural analogue of F2N8, is most likely located at the level of the ester groups and glycerol residues of phospholipids with the probes' ESIPT reaction site (3-hydroxyl and 4-carbonyl groups) at the level of sn_2 carbonyls of phospholipids, similar to F2N8^{23,27}. As a consequence, stronger hydration of the probe environ-

ment in EYPG vesicles causes a slower proton-transfer dynamics than the EYPC vesicles and vice-versa. In the EYPG vesicles with a negative surface charge (Fig. 1), electrostatic repulsion of uncompensated negative charges of the phosphate groups makes the membranes easily accessible to water, thereby, causing a strong hydration of the probe binding site. On the other hand, for the neutral EYPC vesicles comprising zwitterionic phosphatidylcholine (PC, Fig. 1), these negative charges are compensated by the neighbouring $-N^+(CH_3)_3$ groups, which condense the membrane making it less accessible to water^{23,24}.

Kinetics of solvent relaxation :

A continuous time-dependent Stokes shift (TDSS) of the short-wavelength emission band to the red (Figs. 7 and 8) demonstrates solvent relaxation around the N* form in the lipid bilayer of LUVs. Time-dependent decay of the solvent correlation function, $C(t)$ gives quantitative information on the kinetics of solvent relaxation. The $C(t)$ functions for EYPC and EYPG bilayers are satisfactorily fitted with a bi- or tri-exponential function :

$$C(t) = \{a_1 \exp(-t/\varphi_1) + a_2 \exp(-t/\varphi_2) + a_3 \exp(-t/\varphi_3)\} \quad (4)$$

where a_1, a_2, a_3 are the pre-exponential coefficients and φ_1, φ_2 and φ_3 are the solvent relaxation time constants.

Whereas, the decay of the solvent correlation function is bi-exponential for the EYPG vesicles with two relaxation components of 112 ps and 1.34 ns (Table 3), it is tri-exponential for the EYPC vesicles with solvent relaxation components of 58 ps, 435 ps and 4.34 ns, respectively. The average relaxation time, $\langle \tau_s \rangle$, of ~ 0.9 ns for the F2N12S dye in the large unilamellar vesicles of EYPG reveals that the solvent relaxation occurs on a much slower timescale (Fig. 9) in the EYPC vesicles with an average relaxation time of ~ 1.38 ns (Table 3). These mean relaxation times in the nanosecond time scale are much slower than solvent relaxation in pure water which commonly occurs in the sub-picosecond time scale⁴⁵ and may be attributed to a time dependent reorientation of the molecular domains of phospholipids and water molecules surrounding the fluorescent dye^{46,47}. The average relaxation time decreases from 1.38 to 0.9 ns on going from the lipid vesicles of EYPC to EYPG due to increasing hydration of the phospholipid ester carbonyl groups in the vicinity of the F2N12S dye. Thus, there are greater

number of relaxing water molecules in the lipid vesicles of EYPG than EYPC, to cause a faster collective response of the molecular domains of phospholipids and water molecules in the former than the latter, which gives rise to the slower average relaxation of the dye environment in EYPC compared to EYPG. As a consequence, the demonstration of the higher average relaxation time (~ 1.38 ns) for the EYPC vesicles than EYPG (~ 0.9 ns) indicates to the greater extent of hydration of the lipid bilayer in the negatively charged EYPG vesicles compared to the neutral EYPC vesicles.

Conclusions

TRES demonstrates the existence of both ESIPT and solvent relaxation in the photophysics of the F2N12S dye in the large unilamellar vesicles of EYPC and EYPG. The dynamics of ESIPT is faster in EYPC than the EYPG vesicles, whereas solvent relaxation is slower in the former when compared to the latter. The opposite trend in variation of the ESIPT and solvent relaxation dynamics reveals the important role of differential hydration of the neutral EYPC and the negatively charged EYPG vesicles in modulation of their dynamics. Stronger hydration of the EYPG vesicles than the EYPC vesicles causes stronger intermolecular H-bonding perturbation of the intramolecular hydrogen bond between the 3-hydroxy and the 4-carbonyl group in F2N12S, thereby, resulting in a much slower ESIPT dynamics in the former compared to the latter. On the other hand, the relaxation dynamics of the dye environment becomes faster in the lipid bilayer of EYPG vesicles owing to its greater extent of hydration, compared to the EYPC vesicles. The stronger hydration of the EYPG vesicles with a negative surface charge arises due to an electrostatic repulsion of the uncompensated negative charges of the phosphate groups, which makes the membranes easily accessible to water. But, for the neutral EYPC vesicles composed of zwitterionic PC, the negative charges of the phosphate groups are compensated by the positively charged $-N^+(CH_3)_3$ groups which condense the membrane, thereby, hindering its access to water.

Acknowledgement

RD is grateful to his former colleagues Dr. Klymchenko, Dr. Duportail and Professor Mely in CNRS, France and Universite de Strasbourg for their kind help and co-operation.

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